

PAPILLONS

**Plastic in Agricultural Production:
Impacts, Lifecycles and LONG-term Sustainability**

NEWSLETTER #2 JANUARY 2023

**Field & laboratory
experiments in full
swing**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000210

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HELLO AND WELCOME BACK!

A happy New Year, and welcome to the next newsletter of the PAPILLONS H2020 project!

Recently, we have been contributing with our work to limit the existing knowledge gaps, given that still so little information is known on the behavior, and the long-term effects of plastic in agricultural soils. In the meantime, the Plastics Treaty has been evolving and the European Union is developing its own ideas on (micro)plastics and soils, while at the same time plastic residues are increasingly present in the public debate.

In this newsletter you will find some relevant updates and news on the PAPILLONS project, such as Stakeholder meetings, or our latest publications. Feel free to read through it and contact us if you wish to contribute to the project as a stakeholder, or want to learn more about micro & nanoplastics in agricultural soil.

- PAPILLONS TEAM

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ABOUT PAPILLONS

PAPILLONS (entitled 'Plastic in Agricultural Production: Impacts, Life-cycle and LONG-term Sustainability') is a research project supported by the European Commission within the EU Horizon 2020 programme.

Our consortium is built of 20 partners from 12 countries, who represent the cutting edge of research into agricultural plastic use and impacts in Europe. We comprise a network of world leading experts, including excellence in agronomy, ecotoxicology, soil, animal and plant ecology, material sciences, social sciences, economics and environmental chemistry.

Plastics are becoming increasingly important in European agricultural production. However, many uses of plastics and different farming practices can result in the release of debris with a range of different properties, potential bioactivity, and impacts on soil properties. The long-term impacts of agricultural plastic materials on soil ecosystem quality and functioning, and agricultural sustainability is yet uncharted and unknown.

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The knowledge and understanding of mechanisms and processes controlling releases, behaviour, fate and impacts of different macro, meso, micro and nanoparticles as well as their chemical additives and transformation products on soil ecosystem and its productivity is mostly missing.

What PAPILLONS aims at is to **understand the impacts of the use of plastic materials in EU agricultural soil, i.e., the release of micro & nano-plastics and chemicals and how soil health & productivity is affected.** This way it can contribute to knowledge development and deliver information for farmers, industries, regulators and policy makers to introduce practices, products and instruments that guarantee the safe & sustainable use of agricultural plastics in our soil systems.

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While the majority of micro & nanoplastic research has been concentrated on the marine environment, soils may represent the largest global environmental reservoirs of micro(nano)plastic.

Our goal is to study the sources, behaviour and ecological effects of micro- and nanoplastics in agricultural soils, resulting from the use of agricultural plastics. Our aim is to limit the existing knowledge gaps by our research and to become a “one-stop-shop” of easily digestible information on micro and nano plastics in particular, and on plastic pollution in agricultural soils in general.

Should you have an opinion or expertise on the subject and wish to contribute to the development of our Knowledge Hub with your views featured then do not hesitate to contact us!

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OUR WORK:

PAPILLONS members have also contributed to the Consultation on preparation of an EU-wide policy framework on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics. The aim of the Consultation has been to include the views of citizens, consumers and expert stakeholders in the preparation of an EU-wide Policy framework applying to biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics. Lately the use of plastics within our agricultural practices has had an exponential increase.

While the various polymer types are used in different phases of the agricultural production cycle, when their use is incorrectly managed, it can lead to different - often detrimental - environmental impacts. PAPILLONS latest scientific publication is about answering to the need to have an applied and simplified methodology to manage agricultural plastics monitoring and planning. [Click here for more!](#)

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REFERENCE MATERIALS

We are happy to announce that the PAPILLONS project has managed to create batches of custom-designed reference materials of micro & nanoplastics (MNPs) produced from common polymer types for agricultural plastics (APs) used in European agriculture, which now can be used for reliable testing, assessment, and other research purposes.

Moreover, this involves using not only virgin but representative, recycled agricultural plastics materials too. With this work, the PAPILLONS project manages to supply MNP reference materials not only to the different parts of its own research activities but can share them with the outside world too, where demand for such products is high.

Interested in our catalogue for ordering batches of MNP (micro- and nanoplastics) reference materials? [Contact us here.](#)

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LATEST EXPERIMENTS

PAPILLONS is conducting a pan-European large field-scale experiment. During October and November, researchers from institutes in Finland, Germany, Spain, Norway, and the Czech Republic undertook sampling along a series of agricultural fields.

These included reference fields, where APs, compost or biosolids have never been used, as well as fields where AP & biosolids have been used within the last 10 years or are currently being used. Researchers in Greece and Italy are expected to conduct the sampling in the coming months.

PAPILLONS investigated the effects of environmentally relevant low, medium, and high concentrations of weathered LLDPE and PBAT-starch particles on seed germination and on plant growth.

With the CLIMECS system, the PAPILLONS research project also performs mesocosm studies. Regarding the second experiment, its objective is to elucidate the processes and factors controlling the behavior and effects of microplastics on soil properties, soil biodiversity, and ecosystem service.

Photo taken by Julián Martín de la Sierra © 2022

Photo taken by Laura J. Zantis © 2022

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RESULTS OF A TERRITORIAL ANALYSIS

In the latest scientific publication of PAPILLONS, this study focuses on a territorial analysis, performed using a Geographic Information System (GIS) in an agricultural area of the Apulia region in Southern Italy. Areas of agricultural plastic waste production were identified through land-use maps. The application of plastic waste indices to different crop types and plastic products allowed quantifying and georeferencing actual plastic waste production.

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CONSORTIUM MEETING IN ATHENS

On the 10th of October, the PAPILLONS H2020 research project met in Athens for its first in-person Consortium meeting to review their pioneering research on soil micro & nano plastics (MNP). While other separate meetings have taken place amongst some of the Consortium partners, this occasion was the first time the whole Consortium has had the opportunity to discuss physically together at the same time and space. Our partners managed to deliver through the excellent coordination of the team at NIVA and our hosting partner, the Agricultural University of Athens, for whom without this event could not have taken place! We have had a successful General assembly and Executive Board Meeting, as well as a joint PAPILLONS/MINAGRIS Stakeholder Forum, (see next page). With such a full schedule, the days were intense. No stones were left unturned! Multiple research topics such as single species tests, chemical additive analyses, or field plot experiments were on the agenda. During the four days long meetings, our researchers managed to not only discuss the project's progress, and talk through its next steps, but to get to know each other better too, and thus formulate a truly European research project. Finally, throughout these days, each Working package has had the opportunity to explain its project status and exchange with other partners on key cross-cutting issues.

The PAPILLONS Consortium meets for the first time in person in Athens

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PAPILLONS-MINAGRIS JOINT FORUM

As a follow-up to our first joint stakeholder forum meeting with the MINAGRIS research project, the PAPILLONS project has organized the next such event on the 14th of October in sunny Athens. Various stakeholders and organizations, who have an interest in agricultural plastics, were invited to attend the event from all over the world, resulting in over 250 people registering online as well as stakeholders in person in Athens at the same time. The topic of the Forum was: Plasticulture: an international perspective on environmental sustainability. We aimed to provide our international stakeholders an opportunity to gain insights and participate in the debate on international policy developments on the use of plastic in agriculture. The event came at a very relevant time in terms of policymaking. The first session of the Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee (INC1) to develop an internationally legally binding instrument on plastic pollution is soon upcoming this November, while the EU was working to establish a clear policy framework on biobased, biodegradable, and compostable plastics as well. Our scientists have therefore presented the latest updates from their research activities on the use, diffusion, management, and ecological impacts of agricultural plastics emerging from PAPILLONS and MINAGRIS projects, and other research activities.

Stakeholders from various sectors came together to share their insights and experiences

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IN THE MEDIA:

PAPILLONS has launched its [Youtube channel!](#) This platform features videos, where we aim to introduce the PAPILLONS in a video format as well, and give insights into our research and the topical issues of agricultural plastics and soils. Do not hesitate to subscribe to our channel !

In this newsletter, you will find an [interview with Sylwia Adamczyk](#). Sylwia works as a researcher at Natural Resources Institute Finland. Her role in Work Package 4 is to study physiological and biochemical indicators in plant material exposed to plastics on the scale of cell cultures, microcosms, and field studies.

As part of a selected group of EU-funded projects, PAPILLONS participated at this year's [ECOMONDO conference](#), which is annual trade fair for the green and circular economy. Our researchers took the floor on how PAPILLONS is contributing to the EU Plastics Strategy.

Plastics nowadays can be found everywhere, even in the human body. In fact, have you ever thought of what is your average daily intake rate of microplastics? If you want to know the correct answer, then read the article of one of the PAPILLONS scientists!

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IN THE MEDIA:

PAPILLONS has participated at the final conference of LIFE project BioTHOP, where one of the PAPILLONS scientists introduced the research project to the online audience.

PAPILLONS scientists have written multiple articles in the Käytännön Maamies expert journal such as the "Plastics cause benefits and harm in agriculture", and "The impacts of microplastics in soil - only little is known".

OUR COLLEAGUES:

The MINAGRIS project is another EU funded Horizon 2020 project on agricultural plastic use. They assess the impact of plastic debris in agricultural soils on biodiversity, plant productivity and ecosystem services and their transport and degradation in the environment. PAPILLONS will be holding joint stakeholder forum events with MINAGRIS.

International Knowledge Hub Against Plastic Pollution's (IKHAPP) mission is to collect, critically analyse and disseminate scientific knowledge to support effective policies and actions to fight plastic pollution globally. By providing a common platform, IKHAPP will give voice to this community.

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WHO WE ARE:

Norwegian Institute for Water Research

AGRICULTURAL
UNIVERSITY OF
ATHENS

S Y K E

Finnish Environment Institute

NATURAL RESOURCES
INSTITUTE FINLAND

UNIVERSITÄT
KOBLENZ · LANDAU

FARM
EUROPE

VRIJE
UNIVERSITEIT
AMSTERDAM

MASARYK
UNIVERSITY

Freie Universität Berlin

iPCB ISTITUTO PER I
POLIMERI
COMPOSITI E
BIOMATERIALI

University of Ljubljana

UNIVERSITY OF
CHEMISTRY AND TECHNOLOGY
PRAGUE

instituto
imdea
agua

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI DI BARI
ALDO MORO

UNIVERSITÄT
BAYREUTH

Universiteit
Leiden
The Netherlands

 JÜLICH
Forschungszentrum

UNIVERSITÄT **BONN**

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